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METHODS FOR INVESTIGATION OF THERMOPHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF UNDERGROUND EXTERNAL BARRIER STRUCTURES OF BUILDINGS

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ANNOTATION

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 16, 2005 "On further development of housing construction and the market" focuses on improving the quality of construction and reducing material consumption. The program of scientific and technical development of construction for 2017-2022 and the period up to 2025 stipulate the need to reduce the volume of underground work and reduce the cost of this work. It is well known that energy saving in modern housing and housing operation remains a pressing problem. The main direction of the complex programs developed in this area is the development and application of architectural solutions that provide energy savings in buildings, as well as increase their level of thermal protection. The evidence stated above shows that doing this research is a requirement of the day, the goal is to "develop energy efficiency of the basement of residential buildings" by developing constructive solutions for thermal insulation of basement walls.

Keywords: exterior, barrier structures, wall, thermal physics, condensation, thermal conductivity, expanded polystyrene, optimal thickness, humidity

1. Introduction. The properties of resistance to heat transfer of underground external barrier structures of buildings are directly related to their moisture condition, because when the moisture content of the construction material increases, its thermal conductivity also increases. Excess moisture also reduces the long-term durability of

the structure, and has a negative effect on the sanitary-hygienic condition of the environment in the room surrounding the structure.

There are many reasons for dampness in underground external barrier structures. They include:

- construction moisture, moisture that enters the structure during the construction of the building;

- ground moisture enters the structure due to capillary absorption of moisture from the ground;

- operational humidity, humidity related to the technological process carried out in the room, which can affect the structure;

- sorption moisture, moisture absorbed from the air depending on the hygroscopic properties of the material.

Moisture conditions in multi-layer constructions can be related to the phenomenon of condensation. Condensation is observed both on the surface of the structure and in its inner layers.

Table 1.1 provides information on the sorption properties of the materials that make up the wall structure we want to conduct research on.

Table 1.1

Values of sorption moisture ω for wall materials, % [3]

Материал	Зичлик, кг/м ³	Relative air humidity φ , %									
		10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Brick	1700	0,01	0,03	0,04	0,05	0,07	0,1	0,16	0,24	0,36	0,55
Penoplast	15	0,9	1,8	2,5	3,3	4,1	5	6	7,6	11	17
lime-sand plaster	1600	0,3	0,4	0,5	0,7	0,8	1,0	1,3	1,8	2,5	3,5

When calculating the moisture regime of the external barrier structures of the building, especially when performing these calculations in the EHM, it is considered appropriate to give the above law in an analytical form. Many empirical formulas have been proposed for the mathematical representation of the laws of dependence of sorption moisture ω on air relative humidity φ . Almost all of these formulas are recommended for the 40% to 100% relative humidity range, given that indoor and outdoor relative humidity is typically less than 40%.

M. Mahmudov recommended the following formula for the mathematical representation of the laws of dependence of both sorption humidity and desorption humidity ω on air relative humidity φ

$$\omega = \frac{a + b \cdot \varphi}{1 - c \cdot \varphi} \quad (1.1)$$

Here, the value of σ in the variable function $(1 - \sigma \cdot \varphi)$ (which varies between 0 and 1) is determined for each material using a multiple stepwise regression analysis using the successive approximation method. Coefficients a and b in the formula are determined by the method of least squares. When choosing the value of σ , the residual dispersion S_o^2 , which occurs due to the differences between the experimental values of sorption moisture and the calculated values determined using the formula (1.1), is taken as a criterion.

Values of coefficients a and b in the formula (1.1) determined using the method of least squares for the case where $c = 0.79$ for a brick term with volume weight $\gamma_0 = 1700 \text{ kg/m}^3$ are $a = -0.0281$ and $b = 0.1431$. Then the empirical formula of the sorption isotherm for a brick thermal mass with a volume weight $\gamma_0 = 1700 \text{ kg/m}^3$

$$\omega_x = \frac{0,1439 \cdot \varphi - 0,0281}{1 - 0,79 \cdot \varphi} \quad (1.2)$$

can be written as

The results of testing the adequacy of this equation are presented in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2.

Statistics when $\gamma_0 = 1700$ for a brick term with $\gamma_0 = 1700 \text{ kg/m}^3$

№	φ	ω_3	ω_x	$\omega_x - \omega_3$	$\varepsilon_i, \%$	$\varepsilon_{\text{ypr}}, \%$	F_x	F_T
1	0,4	0,05	0,043	-0,007	-16,06	5,01	607,711	4,95
2	0,5	0,07	0,725	0,025	3,45			
3	0,6	0,1	0,11	0,01	9,7			
4	0,7	0,16	0,162	0,002	1,55			
5	0,8	0,24	0,236	-0,004	1,47			
6	0,9	0,36	0,351	-0,009	2,57			
7	1,0	0,55	0,551	0,001	0,28			

Here, the relative error at each experimental point was determined by the following formula:

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{\omega_x - \omega_3}{\omega_x} \cdot 100\%.$$

The average relative error was determined by the following formula:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{ypr}} = \frac{\sum |\varepsilon_i|}{n}, \%$$

The calculated value of Fisher's criterion is with the following formula

$$F_x = \frac{S_{\omega}^2}{S_o^2},$$

where S_{ω}^2 is the dispersion of experimental values of sorption moisture relative to its average; is determined by the following formula:

$$S_{\omega}^2 = \frac{1}{n-1} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i \right)^2 / n \right]; \quad (1.3)$$

$n=7$ - total number of experimental points;

ω_i - values of sorption moisture at experimental points, %;

S_o^2 - dispersion (residual dispersion) due to differences between experimental and calculated values of sorption moisture; its value is determined by the following formula:

$$S_o^2 = \frac{1}{n-k} \sum_{i=1}^n (\omega_i - \tilde{\omega}_i)^2. \quad (1.4)$$

$\tilde{\omega}_i$ - values of sorption moisture determined by the formula (1.2), %;

$k=2$ - is the number of unknown coefficients in the regression equation.

The tabular value of Fisher's criterion F_T is determined from the table according to the degrees of freedom of variances $n-1=6$ and $n-k=5$. With calculated and tabulated values of Fisher's criteria $F_x \geq F_T$, the regression equation (1.2) is adequate with a reliable probability of 0.95 and can be used to predict the moisture content of the material depending on the relative humidity of the air.

Values of coefficients a and b in the formula (1.1) determined by the method of least squares for the case of $s=0.84$ for foam plastic with volume weight $\gamma_0=15$ kg/m³ are $a=1.9355$ and $b=0.7897$. Then the empirical formula of the sorption isotherm for foam plastic with a volume weight $\gamma_0=15$ kg/m³

$$\omega_x = \frac{1,9355 + 0,7897 \cdot \varphi}{1 - 0,84 \cdot \varphi} \quad (1.5)$$

can be written as

The results of checking the adequacy of the equation (1.5) are presented in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3.

Statistics at $S=0.84$ for penonlast with $\gamma_0=15$ kg/m³

№	φ	ω_3	ω_x	$\omega_x - \omega_3$	$\varepsilon_i, \%$	$\varepsilon_{\text{пр}}, \%$	F_x	F_T
1	0,4	3,3	3,39	0,09	2,67	1,83	1028,12	4,95
2	0,5	4,1	4,018	-0,082	-2,04			
3	0,6	5,0	4,858	-0,142	-2,93			
4	0,7	6,0	6,039	0,039	0,65			
5	0,8	7,6	7,827	0,227	2,9			
6	0,9	11,0	10,845	-0,155	-1,43			
7	1,0	17,0	17,032	0,032	0,19			

Experimental and calculated graphs of the sorption isotherm for foam plastic with a bulk density $\gamma_0=15 \text{ kg/m}^3$ are shown in Fig. 1.4. As can be seen from the graph, there is a strong correlation between the humidity ω of foam plastic with $\gamma_0=15 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and the relative humidity φ in the form of (

Values of coefficients a and b in formula (3.1) determined using the method of least squares for a lime-sand mixture with volume weight $\gamma_0=1600 \text{ kg/m}^3$ for the case where $s=0.77$ are $a=0.2088$ and $b=0.595$. Then the empirical formula of the sorption isotherm for the lime-sand mixture with the volume weight $\gamma_0=1600 \text{ kg/m}^3$

$$\omega_x = \frac{0,2088 + 0,595 \cdot \varphi}{1 - 0,77 \cdot \varphi} \quad (1.6)$$

can be written as.

The results of checking the adequacy of the equation (1.6) are presented in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4.

Statistics at $s=0.77$ for lime-sand mixture with $\gamma_0=1600 \text{ kg/m}^3$

№	φ	ω_3	ω_x	$\omega_x - \omega_3$	$\varepsilon_i, \%$	$\varepsilon_{\text{пр}}, \%$	F_x	F_T
1	0,4	0,7	0,646	-0,054	-8,4	3,5	344,074	4,95
2	0,5	0,8	0,823	0,023	2,83			
3	0,6	1,0	1,052	0,052	4,92			
4	0,7	1,3	1,356	0,056	4,15			
5	0,8	1,8	1,783	-0,017	-0,93			
6	0,9	2,5	2,425	-0,075	-3,11			
7	1,0	3,5	3,495	-0,005	-0,14			

The moisture regime of external multi-layer barrier structures of buildings largely depends on the vapor permeability coefficient μ of the material. The coefficient of vapor permeability will not have a constant value, it can change depending on temperature and humidity. As the temperature decreases, the vapor permeability coefficient of the material decreases. The effect of moisture in the material is the same: as moisture increases, so does μ . Материаллар учун буғ ўтказувчанлик коэффициентининг температура ва намликка боғлиқ ҳолда

ўзгарувчанлиги маълум факт бўлса ҳам, ташқи тўсиқ конструкцияларнинг намлик режимини ҳисоблашларда бу коэффициентнинг қиймати ўзгармас деб қабул қилинади.

2. The main part. The method of determining the heat transfer resistance of barrier structures is based on creating a near-stationary temperature regime in the structure, measuring external and internal air temperatures and temperatures at the boundaries of layers, as well as heat flow density. Based on these obtained data, the heat transfer resistance of the structure and its layers is determined.

The length and width of the part of the wall to be tested in the experiment should not be less than 1.5x1 m. The external walls of the existing building were used in our research. The amount of heat flow passing through the tested part of the wall can be determined using fixed or portable ITP-11 thermometers. In order to determine the moisture content of the researched barrier structure, samples are taken from the part of the wall at a height of 1-1.5 m from the floor using a plumber. Samples can be obtained by cutting soft materials in structural layers. The sampling point for moisture should be located in a homogeneous part of the structure. Samples should be placed in metal bags and weighed on an analytical scale on the same day of sampling. Certain methods are used to dry samples and determine moisture content.

Before starting thermotechnical studies in natural conditions, it is necessary to determine the non-homogeneous areas of the structure that conduct excess heat. Its surface temperature is measured using a thermoscope or researched using a thermal imager.

When measuring temperatures on the surface using a thermoscope, the surface is divided into 50x50 cm square grids. Areas with heat-conducting inserts are divided into smaller squares, taking into account the specifics of the construction. The temperature is measured in the corners of these squares, and the values are written on sketches drawn on paper. Isotherms are formed by connecting points with the same temperature, and the configuration and dimensions of the isothermal zones are determined. This work can be done from inside the building.

Thermosensors or thermocouples are installed according to predetermined schemes according to the cross-section of the structure. In this case, a hole is first made for each sensor to be installed inside the wall. It is not possible to place all thermocouples in one continuous hole, it can lead to an error in determining the thermal resistance of the layers.

It is recommended to carry out research in at least two locations of the structure with the same solution, if possible.

In order to determine the temperature of the internal and external air near the structure, thermometers are installed at a distance of 100 mm from its internal and external surfaces. Their number should be at least 2

3. The final part. In the study of heat transfer resistance of barrier structures in natural conditions, the differences that occur in the layers due to the difference between the external and internal air temperatures are used. In this case, the internal temperature is kept in a stationary state as much as possible in various ways. Research should be conducted during the period when the difference between the daily average values of indoor and outdoor air temperatures is at least 100C. 6 days after the beginning of the measurement work, without stopping the tests, the initial results are processed in order to determine the error level of the determination of the thermal resistance. Experiments can be stopped when a fixed error rate is reached.

In the absence of devices that automatically record the necessary data, the values of temperatures and heat flow are measured manually every 3 hours (at 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21) continuously during the day. It is also possible to determine the values of relative air humidity every 6 hours (0, 6, 12, 18). Wind speeds and directions can be measured at a distance of 1.5 to 2 times the height of the building 4 times a day at the times indicated above.

This information can be obtained from nearby weather stations.

The overall heat transfer resistance R_0 of the external barrier structure under study is determined using the following formula for its homogeneous zone:

$$R_0 = \frac{t_e - \tau_e}{q_\phi} + \frac{\tau_e - \tau_H}{q_\phi} + \frac{\tau_H - t_H}{q_\phi} . \quad (1.7)$$

Here t_e and t_H are indoor and outdoor air temperatures, respectively average value for the measurement period, °C;

τ_e and τ_H - respectively, the average value of the temperature of the internal and external surfaces of the structure for the period of measurement, °C;

q_ϕ is the average value of heat flow for the period of temperature measurements, Вт/м².

The thermal resistance R_{cn} of individual layers of the structure is determined by the following formula:

$$R_{cn} = \frac{\Delta\tau}{q_\phi} , \quad (1.8)$$

where $\Delta\tau$ is the temperature difference at the layer boundaries, °C.

In order to compare the actual heat transfer coefficient of the material used in the construction with the value in the project, the heat transfer coefficient of the layer material is determined by the following formula:

$$\lambda = \frac{\delta}{R_{ct}}, \quad (1.9)$$

where δ is the thickness of the layer, m.

In studies conducted in natural conditions, 1 day is accepted as a calculation measurement period. When processing the received data, the temperature increase for each day is initially determined:

$$\Delta\tau_{cym.i} = \tau_{hi} - \tau_{h(i-1)}, \quad (1.10)$$

where τ_{hi} is the average temperature of the outer surface of the enclosing structure for the considered day, determined with an accuracy of 2 decimal places, °C;

The average temperature of the outer surface of the $\tau_{h(i-1)}$ -shaped barrier structure a day before the day under consideration, determined with an accuracy of 2 decimal places, °C

Days with a value of $\Delta\tau_{cym.i}$ not greater than +1.50S are selected for processing. In addition, the following condition is required for all days accepted for processing:

$$\left| \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta\tau_{cym.i} \right| \leq 0,4 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}, \quad (1.11)$$

where n is the number of accepted days.

For each of the received days, the value of the heat transfer resistance R_{0i} is calculated. The average value of R_{0i} is taken as the final $\bar{R}_0$ value of heat transfer resistance. When calculating the results of the measurements, absolute errors with a reliable probability of 67% are also shown in $R_{0i} - \bar{R}_0$ values. R_{0i} 's versus $\bar{R}_0$'s in each experiment is the following

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{R_{0i} - \bar{R}_0}{\bar{R}_0} \cdot 100 \% \quad (1.12)$$

relative error determined by + 40% is required.

The unshifted variance S^2 of R_{0i} values relative to the average value $\bar{R}_0$ is determined using the following formula:

$$S^2 = \frac{\sum (R_{0i} - \bar{R}_0)^2}{n-1} . \quad (1.13)$$

Based on the results obtained for all days of testing, the absolute error for a series of measurements is determined by the following formula:

$$\Delta \bar{R}_0 = \sqrt{\frac{S^2}{n}} . \quad (1.14)$$

The total relative error of measurement results ε is calculated by the following formula:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta \bar{R}_0}{\bar{R}_0} \cdot 100 \% . \quad (1.15)$$

This value should not exceed 8%, otherwise measurements of temperatures on the wall will continue

4. Conclusion. The moisture regime in brick walls of existing buildings that have been in operation for many years can be considered to have reached a quasi-stationary state. In order to increase the energy efficiency, it is possible to use certain methods of calculating the moisture regime for the stationary state in the calculation study of the influence of the thermal insulation installed on them and the structural layers added to the main structure on the moisture regime of the wall.

The actual and estimated heat transfer resistance of the 1.5-brick brick wall, plastered with 20 mm thickness on both sides, which we intend to increase energy efficiency, is much greater than the required value of the heat transfer resistance $R_0^{TP} = 0,67 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{C} / \text{BT}$ determined for the city of Samarkand based on the sanitary and hygienic requirements of the wall, so the existing wall fully meets the thermotechnical requirements for winter conditions.

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